

A Modular Aquatic Robot Inspired by Anguilliform Locomotion

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Abstract—This article presents an aquatic snake robot capable of swimming on the water surface. It has a modular architecture, with identical and independent modules to enhance its maintainability and adaptability to different aquatic environments or tasks. Its design and control algorithm allow swimming at high speed and enable the control of the swimming direction. Moreover, the robot has sensors for obstacle detection and avoidance, crucial for autonomous navigation. The experimental tests demonstrated the robot’s functionality and showed its ability to swim at high speed with extraordinary agility, making this robot a promising solution for applications in complex and unstructured environments. This aquatic snake robot represents a significant novelty in underwater robotics because it is a flexible solution useful for different applications such as environmental monitoring or search and rescue missions.

Index Terms—Aquatic snake robot, Anguilliform swimming, Bioinspired design, Underwater robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

Swimming in environments with obstacles and tight spaces poses significant challenges for conventional robots and autonomous vehicles. Conversely, aquatic snakes and eels display remarkable agility in such environments, inspiring the design of swimming robots [1], [2]. Aquatic snakes and eels adopt the anguilliform locomotion strategy to swim, which consists of moving their body to form a wave that travels from their head to their tail, pushing backward the surrounding water, and receiving thrust for momentum conservation. Their slender, flexible bodies make this swimming strategy suitable for confined spaces where rapid turning and obstacle avoidance are required. Thus, robots inspired by these animals are beneficial for operating in restricted locations inaccessible to larger underwater vehicles or humans [3], [4], and have a wide range of applications, including environmental monitoring, infrastructure inspection, search and rescue missions, and surveillance or security tasks [5], [6].

The robot object of this work reproduces this movement thanks to a modular design, being composed of eight modules actuated by servomotors. The main innovation to its design is the waterproofness of the modules, which makes unnecessary the use of an external cover that could create wrinkles, hindering the hydrodynamics. In addition, this robot can achieve high speed and is very robust in challenging environments because its motors are more powerful than those mounted on

other existing robots despite maintaining the same dimensions. Finally, ultrasonic sensors in the robot’s head enable it to detect obstacles, which is another distinctive advantage of this solution.

II. KINEMATICS OF ANGUILLIFORM SWIMMING

For this locomotion strategy, the whole animal’s body is involved in thrust generation and undergoes large deformations. This movement can be mimicked by adopting a series of identical modules connected by cylindrical joints and by giving a sinusoidal motion law with a phase delay to its joints [6]–[8].

A movement with an amplitude constant along the whole body is typical of aquatic snakes and is called lateral undulation. It is characterized by high speed and low energy efficiency, and it can be achieved by rotating the joints according to (1).

$$\theta_i = (1 - e^{-kt})A \sin(\omega t - i\varphi), \quad (1)$$

where θ_i is the joint angle, with $i = 1, \dots, 8$, and N being the total number of joints, equal to 8; ω is the circular frequency, $\varphi = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$ is the wave number, λ is the wavelength, k is a constant determining the initial transient time, A is the amplitude of the movement.

Conversely, a movement with a variable amplitude that increases from the head to the tail is called eel-like motion since it is typical of eels and lampreys. It is characterized by high energy efficiency and low speed, and it is obtained by rotating the joints as reported in (2).

$$\theta_i = (1 - e^{-kt})A \frac{i-1}{N+1} \sin(\omega t - i\varphi), \quad (2)$$

III. DESIGN OF THE ROBOT

This robot is composed of eight identical modules for the body and one bigger module for the head.

A. The body modules

The modules have a buttonhole shape to allow the relative rotation between each module and the following without leaving a large clearance, which would let water pass through and reduce the generated thrust. Modules are independent of each other, and they include an Arduino Nano Every

electronic board, a 2-cell LiPo battery with its charging circuit, a servomotor that can generate a torque of 3.96Nm at 8.4V and has a maximum speed of 60rpm, and a magnetic encoder.

B. The head module

The head has a geometry slightly different from body modules to allow the insertion of several sensors and components and reduce the hydrodynamic drag. The head hosts an Arduino Mega, a 6-axis IMU sensor, an ultrasonic sensor, a Bluetooth module, an SD-card reader, and a LiPo battery with its charging circuit.

C. The robot assembly

The assembled robot is shown in Figure 1. It has an overall mass of 4.98kg, and its total length is 1281mm, while its height and width are 94mm and 60mm.

Fig. 1: The robot assembled.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Forward swimming

The robot reaches a speed of 0.39 m/s for a frequency of 0.9Hz, an amplitude of 30° , and a phase shift of 0.9rad, as shown in Figure 2. For these tests, the average velocity was calculated by attaching the head of the robot to a wire that unwinds as the robot proceeds forward and measuring the traveled distance and the elapsed time.

Fig. 2: Experimental test for $f = 0.9\text{Hz}$, $A = 30^\circ$, $\varphi = 0.9\text{rad}$

The robot has been tested with different kinematic parameters, and the average speed for each test is shown in Table I.

TABLE I: Average speed with different kinematic parameters

$A[^\circ]$	20	20	30	40	50	60	60
$f[\text{Hz}]$	0.7	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.3
$\varphi[\text{rad}]$	0.5	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
$v_{exp}[\text{m/s}]$	0.21	0.26	0.39	0.37	0.31	0.25	0.38

B. Obstacle avoidance

In Figure 3, it can be observed how the robot detects an obstacle represented by the camera operator from a distance of 1.5m and turns to avoid it.

Fig. 3: Experimental test for obstacle avoidance, $f = 0.5\text{Hz}$, $A = 20^\circ$, $\varphi = \pi/6$

V. CONCLUSION

The snake robot developed in this work integrates powerful motors and sensors for obstacle detection, which constitute a novelty in aquatic snake robots. Thanks to these features and to the low inertia of the modules, the performances of the robot are very promising, allowing potential applications in several fields. Moreover, it is practical from the user's perspective and is completely waterproof since no damage or practical issues emerged from the presence of water during the experiments.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Lighthill, "Hydromechanics of aquatic animal propulsion," *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, vol. 1, pp. 413–446, 1969.
- [2] M. Triantafyllou and G. Triantafyllou, "An efficient swimming machine," *Scientific American*, pp. 64–70, 1995.
- [3] E. Kelasidi, K. Pettersen, J. Gravdahl, S. Stromsoyen, and A. Sorensen, "Modeling and propulsion methods of underwater snake robots," in *2017 IEEE Conference on Control Technology and Applications (CCTA)*, 2017, pp. 819–826.
- [4] J. Sverdrup-Thygeson, E. Kelasidi, K. Petersen, and J. Gravdahl, "A control framework for biologically inspired underwater swimming manipulators equipped with thrusters," in *10th IFAC Conference on Control Applications in Marine Systems CAMS 2016*, 2016.
- [5] E. Kelasidi, P. Liljebäck, K. Pettersen, and J. Gravdahl, "Innovation in underwater robots: Biologically inspired swimming snake robots," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 44–62, 2016.
- [6] A. Crespi, A. Badertscher, A. Guignard, and A. Ijspeert, "Swimming and crawling with an amphibious snake robot," in *2005 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2005, pp. 3024–3028.
- [7] P. Liljebäck, O. Stavdahl, K. Pettersen, and J. Gravdahl, "Mamba - a waterproof snake robot with tactile sensing," in *2014 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, 2014.
- [8] R. Thandiackal, K. Melo, L. Paez, J. Herault, T. Kano, K. Akiyama, F. Boyer, D. Ryczko, A. Ishiguro, and A. Ijspeert, "Emergence of robust self-organized undulatory swimming based on local hydrodynamic force sensing," *Science Robotics*, 2021.